

THE ORIGIN OF COVID-19: A SCIENTIFIC GUIDE

How Does Science Must Categorize
If The COVID-19 is Intentionally Made or Not,
Through The New Intelligent Design <id>?

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(Scientific Science: Official YouTube Channel of the new Intelligent Design <id>)

ABSTRACT

As of this writing, COVID-19 had been infecting almost 400 million people

and counting, had been killing over 5.5 million humans and still counting, had been destroying trillions of US dollars of economy and still going on, had been interrelating (intelligently relating or intentionally relating) from *Alpha* to *Omicron* variants and COVID-19 is causing many suicides due to lockdowns. One of the worst hit of the COVID-19 is the Tokyo 2020 Olympics, in where athletes compete each other without onlooking supporters, audiences, and customers, while the Japanese government had spent billions of US dollars in anticipation of success of the games. In addition, the Tokyo 2020 Olympics was postponed for one year due to COVID-19. So far, no one had ever shown if the COVID-19 had originated naturally (nature) or not (intention). To answer and solve this mystery or dilemma, science needs a universally correct scientific categorization method or technique to pinpointedly nail down the origin of the COVID-19 correctly and prevent future occurrences of destructive virus pandemic. The discoveries from the new Intelligent Design <id> are being proposed to be used as *guide* in dealing and categorizing the topic of origins, especially, the origin of COVID-19.

INTRODUCTION

^{1/5}I do not know if you had read all my science e-books in *Amazon.com* or watch all my YouTube videos or read some of my free science articles in *Zenodo* about the topic of *intelligence (intentional)* and *non-intentional (non-intentional)* and how I derived and discovered them. But I assume that this is your first time to read or hear this info in science, because probably, I am not yet famous! But if you could just quickly jump to this science article in *Zenodo* (link here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5091161>) and knew the basic summarized powerful

scientific explanations of the new Intelligent Design <id>, you could easily understand me. But anyway, probably you will be upset to jump from one place to place, and take your time. So, just stay here since I included in this article the basic summarized derivation of the universal scientific basis of categorizing the COVID-19, as one *X* or one specimen or one topic to be categorized, of its origin, by/from the powerful scientific explanation from the new Intelligent Design <id>. I also included some information that could clarify further my explanations on why the new Intelligent Design <id> is powerful and added clarification so that you will not be confused - so that you could follow my explanations about this GUIDE in categorizing the COVID-19. But I suggest that after you read this article, you go back again to the link that I have shared you above and reread this article, and you will see how powerful the new Intelligent Design <id> in science.

²Because I am not yet famous, and because you did not have any clue on my scientific basis or criteria of categorizing any *X* in science, and sorry for that, to me, this science article that you are reading is just the continuation of the other article that I had submitted in *Zenodo* titled, ***The New Intelligent Design <id> and Its Powerful Correct Scientific Explanations***, and part of Number **6: APPLICATIONS AND CONFIRMATIONS**. (I had already shared you the link above). Since in that article, I discussed many topics and many examples or applications in both real life and in science on how to use the powerful explanations of the new Intelligent Design <id>. I think you will enjoy them, since they are too amazing, powerful and correct, testable and part of reality – and I wrote them here for *Zenodo* as FREE article. I made it FREE so that people like you had the chance to know the best scientific discoveries that we have in this century and forward. Of course, you will surely wiggle your head and probably say, “What the heck?! Really?”. The EUREKA time for all of us! Now, in this article, I will be showing you how to categorize the COVID-19, as one topic and one specimen, or *X* from the new Intelligent Design <id>.

³When the *World Health Organization (WHO)* had decided to categorize if COVID-19 is intentionally made (intellen) or non-intentionally made (naturen), the *WHO* had picked “qualified” scientists in dealing with two extremes. Those scientists maybe qualified as biologists, virologists and scientists in some other fields in science

but those scientists had no criteria or no universal boundary line (UBL) between intentional (or intelligently made or non-natural, or non-zoonotic) to non-intentional (natural or zoonotic). Since all (or mostly) of those scientists are followers and supporters of the Theory of Evolution (ToE), in where ToE has no universal dividing line between intelligent/intentional to non-intelligent/non-intentional, then, the logical question is: where did they get their criteria or basis in knowing which is natural and which is non-natural process, without my discoveries? Well, I am the sole discoverer of the differences in science between these two extremes, and I called it the universal boundary line (UBL) between the two (intentionally made COVID-19 or not, as our topic). Where did they get those criteria? Do you think that *WHO* should be including me to scientifically categorize COVID-19 if COVID-19 as intellen or naturen, to help humanity? I wish I could help them but since I am not yet very famous, then, I had to share to you the SCIENTIFIC GUIDE in categorizing with two extremes. And let *WHO*-picked-scientists (or anybody, even you) check if I am scientifically right or wrong.

⁴The new Intelligent Design <id> is **very** powerful in science in explaining two extreme scenarios in reality because the new <id> has its own universal categorization pattern (UCP) or universal boundary line (UBL) between *intentional* (intelligent) to *non-intentional* (non-intelligent), as discussed from these links: (Link 1) science e-book as published in Amazon, <https://www.amazon.com/Intelligent-Design-Turning-Scientific-Upside-ebook/dp/B00HWUX220> and (Link 2) article in *Zenodo*, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5091161>. In those links, the new Intelligent Design <id> had shown to the world its explanatory power, that no other model or theory or idea had ever shown – from the time humans know about science, to the end of human civilization. The new Intelligent Design <id> too could explain and categorize obvious object (*X*), obscure object (*X*) and obtuse object (*X*) that no scientist could ever do, or will never be. Because of the powerful unique capabilities of the new Intelligent Design <id>, the new Intelligent Design <id> could guide scientists or any person, who had the capability to categorize, if the COVID-19 is intentionally made (intellen) to non-intentionally made (naturen), easily and completely.

^{5/5}But let us discuss first the differences between our present science (old

science) versus the science from the new Intelligent Design <id> (new science).

1. Why The Present Science Is Unreliable?

^{1/17}Science in general is reliable (if we could test the explanation, of course!), that is unquestionable, but in nailing the topic of origins and categorizing the two extremes, like between *intelligent* to *non-intelligent* or *intentional* to *non-intentional*, scientists who are conducting science have no explanatory power for these. Which means, they could never categorize the origin of COVID-19 correctly and scientifically. Why?

Science e-Book in Amazon: *The New Intelligent Design <id>, Turning The Scientific World Upside Down*,

<https://www.amazon.com/Intelligent-Design-Turning-Scientific-Upside-ebook/dp/B00HWUX220>

^{2/1.1} Because Science Follows the Theory of Evolution (ToE).

Almost all scientists today, except the scientists from Creation Camp, the ID camp etc., accept that the Theory of Evolution (ToE) is a valid scientific “theory” or “model”, that could explain reality better than its

opponents. Really? And almost all virologists, microbiologists, epidemiologists, especially those who are studying coronaviruses and the likes, are supporters of ToE. They accept that ToE is the best theory in biology or life science, and its related fields.

³But one thing they are afraid to admit is that ToE, as a theory and an explanatory scientific model, has no universal scientific explanation in the topic of origins, or cause and effect - that ToE could never categorize or differentiate or divide between intelligent (intentional) to non-intelligent (non-intentional) **X**. It was Darwin, the founder or pioneer of ToE, who had given those scientists a clue or hint that in nature, two extreme scenarios are not possible, nor even feasible, because according to Darwin, the founder of ToE, millions of years do not permit such kind of differences. Thus, all scientists who support ToE had no explanatory power in dealing with two extremes. Thus, their explanations or categorizations of the origin, for example, of COVID-19, if COVID-19 is naturally made (nature) or non-naturally made (intellen), is always scientifically wrong.

⁴From the Figure below, it shows how Darwin had distorted science and made scientists stupid by giving science a worst categorization pattern between *simple to complex*, and between perfect to imperfect (non-perfect). And as you can see, that Darwin did not use experiment to prove or show his case, but his own reasoning (!), that had no basis at all in science.

⁵When Charles Darwin had explained the origin of the eyes, in his famous book, “On the Origin of Species...”, he claimed that a longer period of time (millions of years) had **changed** a *simple/unperfect* eye to a *complex/perfect* eye ($X = \text{eye}$), giving science a new way of categorizing two opposite scenarios. The two opposing scenarios are: *simple and unperfect to complex and perfect*, respectively. The conclusion from Darwin (and after him), according to his “reasoning”, was that, both *simple eye* and *complex eye* are in the same categorization - no differences, a newer default

Hence it will cause him no surprise that there should be geese and frigate-birds with webbed feet, either living on the dry land or most rarely alighting on the water; that there should be long-toed curlews living in meadows instead of in swamps; that there should be woodpeckers where not a tree grows; that there should be diving thrushes, and petrels with the habits of auks.

Organs of extreme perfection and complication.—To suppose that the eye, with all its inimitable contrivances for adjusting the focus to different distances, for admitting different amounts of light, and for the correction of spherical and chromatic aberration, could have been formed by natural selection, seems, I freely confess, absurd in the highest possible degree. Yet reason tells me, that if numerous gradations from a perfect and complex eye to one very imperfect and simple, each grade being useful to its possessor, can be shown to exist; if, further, the eye does vary ever so slightly, and the variations be inherited, which is certainly the case; and if any variation or modification in the organ be ever useful to an animal under changing conditions of life, then the difficulty of believing that a perfect and complex eye could be formed by natural selection, though insuperable by our imagina-

Online book of Charles Darwin, "On the Origin of Species, On the Preservation of ..."

http://darwin-online.org.uk/converted/pdf/1861_OriginNY_F382.pdf Screen shot image on page

167. Underlined is mine.

explanation. So, the supposed to be *new categorization* in science is actually, a no-categorization at all.

⁶How will you call and handle this situation? When you hire a taxi to bring you to a certain location, and the taxi driver asked you for direction, and you say, "Right corner, please" and the driver went to "Left direction", and when you say "Left corner, please", and the driver went to "Right corner", you will certainly be surprised! You will probably ask the driver if there is a language barrier or the driver is totally deaf. But when the driver told you that "Right direction" and "Left direction" is the same, *a no-categorization at all*, you will certainly call that driver, "STUPID!".

⁷So, the question: *where those scientists, either picked by WHO or other scientists,*

who support ToE, got the idea of correct categorization of two extremes for the topic of origins, knowing that their leader or role model, Darwin, had made it wrong in the very first place? The obvious answer is they borrowed and borrowing those explanations from the concept of intelligence unknowingly, that they themselves rejected as not scientific explanation! Which means, these scientists could never categorize if COVID-19 (or biological cell) is intellen or naturen correctly.

1.2 Because Science Has No Universal Categorization Pattern.

⁸Mathematics is one of many universal languages and anybody could read it as a universal language that could transcend any border or any races, creeds or religions. Scientists and mathematicians and the likes use Mathematics, and they know for sure that Mathematic formulas, equations, theorems etc. are universal.

⁹Categorizing two extreme opposites also needs a universal pattern so that all scientists and all humans could easily categorize two extreme scenarios, like the categorization if the COVID-19 is manmade (intellen) or naturally made (naturen).

¹⁰Those who received funds or grants from governments and others should first nail down the differences between intentional (intelligent) to non-intentional (non-intelligent) before they could conclude if, for example, a biological cell is intentionally made/designed (intellen) or not (naturen), and apply that to COVID-19, if the COVID-19 is intellen or naturen. This is the first logical way to solve two or more opposite extremes.

¹¹But as you can see, that the scientists who support the Biological Evolution, who receive billions of US dollars to do it, do not even bother to nail down the universal differences between *simple* to *complex* or **perfect** to **imperfect (un-perfect)**, but ignored or dismissed them. They probably thought that these two extremes are already settled scientifically since Darwin had used his own “reasoning” and **not** a science experiment. The most probable reason for ignoring the two extremes is that they do not have any answer or no clue whatsoever to nail them down, like Darwin. Or they

probably became religious.

¹²One of the most bizarre and controversial conclusions from Charles Darwin and supporters of the Theory of Evolution (ToE) was that the change (in all species or all living organisms) is un-intentional, uncontrolled, non-intelligence and unguided, which means, the actual scientific definition of Biological Evolution would always be

Biological Evolution or Evolution is an unguided, un-intentional, un-intelligent, non-determined or unregulated biological change in the frequency allele, of gene variants, in a population over generations (with time).

¹³This maybe correct if naturalistic science had already shown the differences between *unguided*, to *guided*, between *non-intentional* to *intentional*, and so on – with experiment. Logical and fair scientist will surely ask, “How can we falsify a no-classification explanation or one-sided explanation?”

¹⁴As you can see, it would be stupidity for any person/scientist to use the concept of ToE in solving if COVID-19 is intellen or naturen, or any *X* that requires the explanation of origin.

1.3 Because Many Scientists Had Tried But Failed

¹⁵In reality, it was the scientists who support the Theory of Evolution (ToE) who had first tried to universally differentiate (as a universal pattern) *simple* to *complex* and perfect to imperfect, from Darwin, but as you can see that Darwin had failed. They failed. Period. His failure was not given too much attention since no scientist had ever tried to nail the difficulty of the universal pattern, as alternative. And the worst reason was that the scientists who support the ToE probably thought that since ToE is a reigning scientific theory or model, which is funded and endorsed by almost all public schools around the world, to think and discover the

universal pattern for two extremes is not badly needed. How will you need the *universal pattern* if the whole world is using ToE as the universal theory that combines the whole fields of science? The world is already using ToE, no need to discover this universal pattern, right?

“Evolution, a fact rather than mere hypothesis, is the central unifying concept in biology. By extension it affects almost all other fields of knowledge and thought and must be considered one of the most influential concepts in Western thought.”
DOUGLAS J. FUTUYMA, 1942 – Evolutionary Biology, 1979 (From: <https://www.famousscientists.org/evolution-quotes/>)

¹⁶People are satisfied with the ToE, people quote ToE, people are teaching ToE and people is using ToE, and people are funding ToE, no need to nail the universal pattern between *simple* to *complex*, between *perfect* to *imperfect*, right?! (Scientifically speaking, that is totally wrong!)

^{17/17}But many scientists like me thought and are thinking that what the scientists of ToE had done is stupidity! As a result, many of those scientists who opposed ToE had tried to nail this universal pattern between two extremes, and some of them used Darwin’s idea of “complex”, believing that Darwin was a genius. Here they are. **Enjoy!**

DERIVATION OF UNIVERSAL BOUNDARY LINE (UBL)

From OTHER GROUPS/CAMPS

^{1/10}On 2014, February, on the debate between Bill Nye and Ken Ham, as uploaded in the *Answer-In-Genesis* YouTube Channel titled “Bill Nye Debates Ken Ham - HD (Official)”, on the *Answer-In-Genesis* compound, Bill

Nye had asked Ken Ham about this,

I'm looking for explanations of the creation of the world, as we know it, based on, what I'm going to call "science". ...things that each of us can do, akin to what we do. We're trying to outguess the characters on murder mystery shows, on crime scene investigation. Play video from 1:48:04,

²Basically, Bill Nye was asking Ken Ham to share the scientific world about Ken Ham's universal categorization model of *created* and *uncreated world (or biblical kinds or universe, or any X)*, for two opposite scenarios, (like the Forensic Study of any crimes on earth), based on the Bible, that is far better than Darwin's categorization method. But the camp of Bill Nye and evolutionary scientists had no universal categorization between the two extremes, that could help scientists to pinpointedly direct the source of the origins of both universe, life, species, kinds or existence.

Screen shot image from YouTube on the debate between "Ken Ham vs Bill Nye". **Debate between Ken Ham and Bill Nye.** <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z6kgvhG3AkI&t=6373s>

³At least, the camp of Creation had already claimed and pinpointedly explained that Jesus Christ, the God Creator, is the Source of the universe, life and existence. Thus, Creation Explanation is more plausible since it is more detailed and specific, than Bill Nye's camp. Did Bill Nye accept that a vacuum is the pinpointedly Source/Origin of universe?

⁴As you can see that if there is NO explanation between two opposites, then, there will be NO scientific explanations – a very powerful clue for any scientist to dare explaining reality in the name of “science”.

⁵I wish that Bill Nye, or any other scientists who dared to fight me scientifically in this topic, should write science article in *Zenodo*, explaining the differences between naturally originated and intentionally originated COVID-19, by using ToE as guide, without borrowing ideas and concept from intelligence. And lets us compare. Would you like you see two clashing scientific explanations? It is fun and educational, right? Tell them to do it and put up here in *Zenodo*! I will wait and ready to battle scientifically!

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RESEARCH

I am interested in the evolution of complex biochemical systems. Despite much progress by science in the past half century in understanding how such systems work, little progress has been made in explaining how they arise. A key issue is that many systems in the cell require multiple components in order to function. I have dubbed such systems “irreducibly complex” (IC). (Behe 1996) The problem that multi-component systems present to a gradualist Darwinian evolutionary framework has been apparent at least since 1871, when the English biologist St. George Mivart wrote of “The Incompetency of ‘Natural Selection’ to Account for the Incipient Stages of Useful Structures.” Put into modern parlance, the problem is that the function of an IC system only appears when the system is essentially complete, frustrating selection by small Darwinian steps.

(Figure 1. A simple illustration of the concept of irreducible complexity. The pictured mousetrap needs all of its parts to work.)

Yet as formidable a barrier as irreducible complexity itself presents to undirected constructive evolution

PUBLICATIONS

Michael Behe, in Lehigh University Web site. Michael Behe, from Lehigh University Website.

<https://www.lehigh.edu/~inbios/Faculty/Behe.html>

⁶Furthermore, scientists in/from the old Intelligent Design (ID) camp, (especially, Michael Behe), that is being endorsed by *Discovery Institute*, had been claiming that to categorize living organisms, or biological cell, for example, science must use *irreducible complexity* (for intentionally designed cell or intellen cell) and *reducible complexity or irreducible simplicity* (for non-intentionally designed cell or naturen cell) – for Biology only. How about for Cosmology or Astronomy or the origins of universe or particle, or in manufacturing, etc? Non-applicable, powerless, and useless, of course. Remember that Behe was eager to nail down the universal categorization because Darwin and ToE had failed to give the world and scientific world a universal pattern to categorize two opposite extremes.

⁷Some scientists, like Stephen Meyer⁴, is claiming that *information, Shannon Information*, (or mis-information? Lol!) could be used in the new scientific categorization process, in Biology only. Thus, any *X* that has a *coded information* is intelligently designed (intellen) or intentionally created (intellen). In addition, any *X* that has *no coded information* is not intelligently designed (naturen) or not intentionally created (naturen). This is from the old Intelligent Design (ID), for Biology only. Again, but how about in Physics or Cosmology or Astronomy, or in economics or business world, etc.? This categorization too is useless and powerless. Not Applicable, too.⁴

THE LATEST

Stephen Meyer and the web site of Discovery Institute. **Stephen Meyer and List of scientists from Discovery Institute online.** <https://www.discovery.org/about/fellows/>

⁸As you can see, the stupidity that had originated from the Theory of Evolution (ToE) had triggered a spiral search for the universal categorization process, and Meyer was one of them! (See some scientists that support the *Discovery Institute* and the old Intelligent Design from this link. <https://www.discovery.org/about/fellows/>)

⁹In addition, scientists from the Reasons to Believe (RTB)⁵, headed by Hugh Ross, had been claiming that the Earth and the Solar system (and universe) had been **fine-tuned** so that life on Earth could possibly exist. This is called the *Anthropic Principle*. Although the phrase “fine-tuned” is a synonym of “intelligence” or “intentional” in reality, therefore, correct, and I will show you later, but the RTB scientists has no universal boundary line between “**fine-tuned X**” to “**not fine-tuned X**” or “**rough-tuned X**”, so that all scientists could confirm and falsify the Anthropic Principle. Thus, scientists

from RTB have no powerful scientific explanation! But once again, it was the failure of ToE that had triggered the scientists from RTB to use “fine-tuning” and “non-fine-tuning” categorization process to explain reality. They should apply this process to COVID-19 and see if that works.

^{10/10}At least, all of these groups (theists and atheists) had tried categorizing two extremes, but they ended up with either one categorization only and no categorization at all! Oh, I wish that Darwin and his supporters had nailed these two extremes by discovering the universal boundary line (UBL) between the two extremes and not mess science, that brought science into stupidity, like a domino effect! And you do not have to read my science article, right? But maybe, I was born to discover them for all of us, for science and for human civilization!

Official Web Site of Reasons to Believe. Reasons To Believe web site. <https://reasons.org/>

2. Why The New Intelligent Design <id> Is Reliable?

^{1/10}As I had said that our present science is wrong when science discusses and talks the topic of origin because of the Theory of Evolution (ToE) and its worst

influence. *The ToE had made science as a stupid system when discussing the origins of two opposite extremes.* Now, the followings are the reasons why the new Intelligent Design <id> is correct and reliable. Why reliable?

2.1 ²Because the new Intelligent Design <id> has universal correct definition of *intelligence to non-intelligence*.

Because of the erroneous explanations from the ToE that had badly influenced many scientists, many scientists had FREELY invented many definitions of *intelligence*, and its Intelligent Quotient (IQ). They had come up with 70 invented definitions of intelligence. 70 definitions of intelligence or probably more for one topic?! How stupid we are! Why they messed the topic of intelligence? Because of those scientists who support ToE and had allegiances to ToE, they had invented 70 definitions of intelligence FREELY! If every definition had a detailed written book that explained each and every definition, and the teacher ask the students to bring those 70 books, so that they could understand *intelligence*, I wonder if the students will never rebel against the stupidity of their schools.

³As you can see from the link below, two researchers had published their finding on the invented *definitions of intelligence*, while using ToE as basis. They had come up with 70 definitions. There are probably 80 invented definitions of intelligence based on ToE.

⁴If they had 70 definitions of *intelligence*, they too also had 70 definitions of *non-intelligence*, and 70 kinds of IQ calculation, further messing the topic of intelligence. And when you asked them ***if the COVID-19 is intelligently made or non-intelligently made***, how will they answer this simple question? There will be no answer for that question.

A Collection of Definitions of Intelligence

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15 June 2007

Abstract

This paper is a survey of a large number of informal definitions of “intelligence” that the authors have collected over the years. Naturally, compiling a complete list would be impossible as many definitions of intelligence are buried deep inside articles and books. Nevertheless, the 70-odd definitions presented here are, to the authors’ knowledge, the largest and most well referenced collection there is.

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arXiv:0706.3639v1 [cs.AI] 25 Jun 2007

Definitions Of Intelligence: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0706.3639.pdf>>

⁵The new Intelligent Design <id> had come up with only *one* universal definition of intelligence, a must, that could explain all the invented 80+ definitions of intelligence erroneously. Those of who you who had read my science e-book in *Amazon* knew probably that I explained this topic in detailed and in clear simple explanation. Again, below will be the shortest, exact, universal, correct, testable, scientific and naturalistic definition of *intelligence* and *non-intelligence*, therefore, all other definitions of intelligence are incorrect. Mark my word for that:

Intelligence = when an agent uses/applies two or more solutions

to a single problem

Non-Intelligence = when an agent or designer uses/applies one solution,
or least number of solutions compared to other agents, to
a single problem

⁶Which means that our knowledge and usage of Intelligence Quotient (IQ) must always conform to the new discoveries from the new Intelligent Design <id>, for if not, science can no longer explain reality correctly, especially the IQ limit that science is using now.

⁷I will be using these two definitions in the origin of COVID-19, as guide, to help our society and science categorize if COVID-19 is intellen or naturen.

2.2 ⁸Because the new Intelligent Design <id> has universal categorization process (UCP) and universal boundary line (UBL) between *intelligence* to *non-intelligence*, or sometimes, I used, *intentional* to *non-intentional*.

⁹The *problem-solution* approach is the only way to be used for categorizing two opposites. Beyond or beside this, probably there will be none. Thus, in this paper, naturalistic science must use this **Universal Categorization Pattern (UCP)** or **Universal Boundary Line (UBL)** to categorize/classify/differentiate all opposing things, events or any *Xs*. Below is the UCP or UBL, as written in many different forms.

Intelligently designed *X* (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intelligently designed *X* (naturen) = problem-solution (F1)

Or

Intentionally designed *X* (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intentionally designed *X* (naturen) = problem-solution (F2)

Or

Intentionally designed X (intellen) = $X + X' + X'$

Non-intentionally designed X (naturen) = $X + X'$ (F3)

in where X is the object or specimen to be categorized as problem, and X' as the support or feature or reinforcement for X .

^{10/10}In addition, (probably the word *intelligence* has a different scientific meaning, but in application or practice for UBL/UCP), the word *intelligence* has a synonym words or phrases such as,

Not Naturally Designed, Unnaturally Made, Created, Smart, Intentional, Controlled, Fine-tuned, Pre-planned, Goal-Oriented, Wise, Genius, Decided, Clever, Brilliant, Bright, Superb, Marvelous, Excellent, Very Good, Handled, Regulated, Determined, Managed, Modulated, Governed, Directed, not Dumb, not Moron and not Foolish.

UNIVERSAL LIMITS or RANGES

^{1/11}As you can see at the above universal pattern, any intentionally designed X (intellen) has always two or more solutions or features. The new Intelligent Design <id> denotes it as “asymmetrical phenomenon”, a detection pattern, since intellen has always this pattern: one Problem (P) with two or more Solutions (S). Whereas, the non-intentionally designed X (naturen) is always a “symmetrical phenomenon”, since it is always one Problem, one Solution only (even failing to solve the Problem is also considered a “Solution”), thus, a *symmetry*. Thus, it predicts that the two scenarios must have a numerical limits or ranges.

²The new Intelligent Design <id> too has an **Initial Universal Limit (IUL)** for everything in the entire realm/existence, to clarify and empirically

quantify the universal scientific categorization process:

For non-intentional/non-intelligence = $0 < P < 1$as natural...(L1)

For non-intentional/Instinct = $1 < Instinct < 1.5$as natural (L2)

For intentional/intelligence = $1.5 < Iprob < 3$as intelligent (L3)

For importance = > 3as important (L4)

For failure or Over Importance = $> 3 < Failure < 1$...as natural (L5)

³(L1) “For non-intentional/non-intelligence = $0 < P < 1$as natural”.

It is the same limit for Natural Probability, i.e., Probability, which has always 99 probability of failures and 1 success. Anything that has no intelligence, no intention and no importance falls into this category. This formula/pattern fits to this limit: *Non-intelligently designed X (naturen) = problem-solution*

⁴(L2) “For non-intentional/Instinct = $1 < Instinct < 1.5$as natural”.

This corresponds to the instinct by both humans and animals, or some natural occurrences that goes beyond the natural/normal expectations. This separates instinct to intelligence/intentional, predicting that all humans (homo sapiens) can have either instincts or intelligence but all animals have instinct only – no intelligence at all. This formula/pattern fits to this limit: *Non-intelligently designed X (naturen) = problem-solution*

⁵(L3) “For intentional/intelligence = $1.5 < Iprob < 3$ as intelligent”.

This limit is the actual limit for Intelligent Quotient (IQ). Only an agent that uses mind (like humans, homo sapiens, or God-Creator) could achieve this limit and beyond this limit. All animals have no intelligence and can never achieve this limit. This formula/pattern or equation fits to this limit: *Intelligently designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution*

⁶(L4) “For importance = > 3as important.”

⁷This limit is solely for importance of any X to survive, or exist or success. Take note that the limit of “success” here is different from “success” in $L1$. This formula or equation fits to this limit: *Intelligently designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution-solution...*

⁸(L5) “**For failure or Over Importance = > 3 < Failure < 1...as natural**”.

When an agent uses too much Solutions (S) and too much Importance to the Problem (P), that the many applied Solutions (S) had caused the system or object (X) to fail. This formula/pattern fits to this limit: *Non-intelligently designed X (naturen) = problem-solution*

⁹I should not be discovering and sharing all my new discoveries if other scientists before me who support ToE had its own correct UCP/UBL or IUL, since we could easily use those techniques in categorizing if COVID-19 is naturally made or had a zoonotic origin or made in the lab.

¹⁰**Take note very carefully**, I would like to clarify and reiterate once again that when the new Intelligence Design <id> uses the word *intelligence*, as discovered through science experiment, **intelligence** is always being used for **absolute good** for existence and good for humans. *Intelligence* is for *good* only, no exception! That is why in my original published science e-book in *Amazon*, I did not even use the word *intention/intentional* to replace or use it as co-explanatory word for *intelligence*, since **intelligence is always for good**.

^{11/11}I normally use *intentional* and *intention* to enhance my explanatory ability and catch your attention, to help you understand me, and to clarify some details in practical life, but the new Intelligent Design <id> always cling and hold to **intelligence**. Now, intentional/intention can have two purposes: bad intention and good intention. But there is no such thing as **bad intelligence** or **good intelligence!** Never and cannot be! Stupid agent never uses intelligence! The usage of intention has two-folds, bad intention and good intention, two possibilities for “intentional”, but in

intelligence, intelligence has only one possibility: good, always for good, absolute good. And we will apply that to COVID-19 if COVID-19 is intellen or naturen.

2.3 Because the new Intelligent Design <id> had experiment and practical applications that really work in nature and in reality.

^{1/2}It would be a stupidity for me to claim in science, **take note: science!**, not religion, if I cannot show it with experiment. From this link, <https://zenodo.org/record/5091161>, in *Zenodo*, I had shown you how the new Intelligent Design <id> is scientifically powerful in explaining many difficult and unexplained scenarios that our current understanding of science could never explain. From the fact that the new Intelligent Design <id> had its own UCP and UBL, and to the fact that these works in reality, and until now, I think no one will ever dare to challenge me. Because if you dare to challenge me, first, you must discover a universal categorization pattern with experiment, since you cannot, for example categorize COVID-19 if it is intentionally made (intellen) or non-intentionally made (naturen) if you do not have this universal pattern for the two extremes, with experiment! That would be impossible.

^{2/2}Either you will borrow a universal pattern from my discoveries or from intelligence, but that too falls into my discoveries of intelligence to non-intelligence. And once you discovered your new universal categorization process, like the universal differences between *perfect* to *imperfect*, with experiment, then, apply it in science and in COVID-19, and let us compare.

3. The Difficulties of Categorizing COVID-19

^{1/14}Since COVID-19 had infected more than 6 million human beings and is killing many people as we speak, then, there is the need to categorize COVID-19, to give logical reason for the death (from COVID-19 infections and from suicides due to worst impact from COVID-19) of those innocent human beings. I do not know about

you but for me, as the discoverer of intelligence, the loss of **precious life** to COVID-19 is more painful, than losing jobs, or losing some freedom to lifestyle, or losing some economic benefits or losing finances. Precious lives must be protected.

²*Personally, I am a Christian, one of God's adopted children. What if those who died due to COVID-19 will be going to biblical **Hell**, an eternal separation from God, the Creator of universe and life, and eternal separation from all good? Those resurrected non-believers (not God's children) will live in an eternal evil and bad environment – no ending.*

³*Actually, humans were created by the God Creator to live in good place or Paradise or Heaven. They were not meant to live in Hell, that is why the Earth has all the things the human needs for survival, happiness and enjoyment. But evil humans are changing Earth to become an initial Hell by not loving their fellow humans and by doing evil things to their fellow humans – two severe violations of the laws and regulations of the God Creator for happy existence. Thus, evil humans must be separated from good humans, a must, to protect good humans from the harm of evil humans. And the place that God had prepared for those separated evil humans is called Hell. In Hell, evil humans will be **FREELY** hurting each other's, as to kill them for anger, (but the mercy of death will not be there), probably drinking their own and others blood and urine to quench their thirst (since drinking water is not available).*

⁴*It is not God who will be punishing them in Hell. He already punished them when He separated evil humans from Him and from good humans. God is just separating good humans to evil humans, so that evil humans can no longer harm good humans. Evil humans will be hurting their fellow evil humans in Hell – they punish themselves by themselves. Although He gave those evil humans fire and worms in Hell to add more pains to those who really wanted to live in Hell, but it is their evil acts to their fellow citizens of Hell that will make them feel the pain and terror of Hell. It is unthinkable in Hell when angry evil humans use fire to cause severe pain to their fellow evil citizens of Hell.*

⁵*God is Love but human likes Hate. God had already given them complete freedom to do evil - in Hell. When evil humans freely do evil things in a secluded place, that is Hell, then, it would be a total disaster to all Hell inhabitants. It would be a total disaster for those who unpreparedly died due to COVID-19! Oh, I wish that all of us could go to Heaven!*

⁶*Wait! Let us talk science! What was the topic? Oh, the difficulties of*

categorizing COVID-19!

⁷But since the specimen, the **X**, to be categorized is a virus, and not a PC or a car or a bicycle, or food, then, the person or the in-charge, who will categorize if the existence of COVID-19 is humanly manipulated (intellen) or not (naturen), must have a thorough knowledge of coronavirus. Since COVID-19, one type of coronaviruses, could not be seen by normal human naked eyes, **first major difficulties**, and the COVID-19 has similarities of symptoms in some other former SARS coronaviruses or an ordinary influenza coronaviruses, then, it would be very difficult for many people to categorize COVID-19, which means, only a handful of trained specialist people could specifically categorize if COVID-19 started from the lab or originated from the wild/nature, if the basis of evidence is the genome of COVID-19. But since the technological advancements and scientific knowledge in our present generation about coronavirus is already widespread or widely known, then, it would be very easy for any scientist, I think, like microbiologists or virologists, to classify the COVID-19. Science had already decoded the human genome. They too had already decoded a virus genome.

⁸The COVID-19 was reportedly started from *Wuhan City, Hubei Province, China*, as reported by the government of China or Communist Chinese Party (CCP), earlier on December 2019. As we all know that the CCP or the Communist China is a secretive and authoritative country, in where CCP does not permit press freedom and does not endorse freedom of speech, unless those freedom conforms to the standard goal of CCP, which means, seeking the truth of the origin of the COVID-19 scientifically and freely, if the COVID-19 started in *Wuhan China* or not, as one scenario, is an impossible task, the **second major difficulties**.

⁹Science is always being conducted or done in a free world, openly, in where all scientists exchange and publish their findings, ideas, discoveries, rebuttals and theories freely. Scientists freely clash ideas and explanations, like iron clashes with iron, intellect clashes with intellect freely. And they publish their findings as “science articles” because they are free to do it. But when science is being suppressed by any government, or there is a fear of government’s censorship (just like in Nazi’s time), then, any scientific sources from that country should be considered **pseudo-science**

and all of those articles should be called “propaganda science”.

¹⁰When an authoritative and secretive country joins the free world in a free exchange of scientific ideas and discoveries, in science, the possibilities that the scientific ideas and discoveries coming from an authoritative countries will be always controlled, limited and censored, thus, *first*, the fear of rebutting them without no bad consequences are probably expected, and *second*, the credibility of science as a system, as system of free exchange of discoveries and ideas, to a free world, is being destroyed. In addition, when these freedoms are being suppressed, especially, to categorize a scientific quest for the origin of COVID-19 that havoc and destroyed human lives like the COVID-19, then, it would be very difficult to categorize the COVID-19, since many people will be very confused if the result is scientific or a propaganda.

¹¹In addition, ***third major difficulties***, since COVID-19 had killed and is killing people worldwide, then, the need to know the origin of the COVID-19 is imperative or a must, then, the topic of origin of COVID-19 is both very emotional and very, very, very delicate, that made the categorization of COVID-19 very difficult. Why very difficult? Since, somebody or someone must pay directly or indirectly for the death of innocent people worldwide from COVID-19 and the worst impact of the loss of loved ones to every family, due to infections and suicides and the destruction of many economies. To tell you the truth, this is the most difficult part in dealing and categorizing COVID-19, since people are dying and still dying because of COVID-19. If there is no death of human beings from COVID-19 infection, then, categorizing COVID-19, if it originated from human manipulation or of nature origin, is very easy, and not even emotional or delicate, like categorizing if a stone originated from nature or made/manipulated by human agent. But not for COVID-19 that is killing people right now.

¹²The ***fourth major difficulty*** is that nobody or no one is willing to accept responsibility for the existence or origin of COVID-19 that had killed 6 million innocent people and is killing more. That is why if there is **no** God-Creator who had created the universe, life and existence, those who died in a ***manmade*** COVID-19 are pitiful and died with no justice here on earth. And those who are responsible for the

release of COVID-19 (if COVID-19 is manmade or manipulated) is/are very happy that they could get rid of those responsibilities here on earth. But the belief that **God-Creator of universe, life and existence does not exist** is not scientific and not even logical. Why? It would take faith (and moral and intellectual suicides) to accept that a no-existence could create or pop-up existence without God or a no-life primordial ocean could create life without God - that would be impossible to think and to test. *(One example of intellectual and linguistic suicides to deny the existence of God-Creator is the origin of the universe or the origin/beginning of the universe's Big Bang. Most, or probably, all atheist scientists or non-theist scientists accept and believe that our present Universe or the Mother Universe, had come from "nothing". But in their scientific definition of "nothing", they define the word "nothing" has "something" on it, not simply nothing but a vacuum that has an activity on it, activity that produced or created the universe ex nihilo by itself, deliberately mis-defining and mis-using the word "nothing" that will mean "something". To them, **nothing** is the same as **something**, in the origin of the universe or Big Bang. And they are asking us to swallow it as science. Why not directly say that NOTHING can produce SOMETHING, and "we cannot scientifically test it, sorry" and be proud of it, instead of mis-using word? And the second intellectual suicide is when a scientist will claim something of an origin of something that had come from nothing without any scientific test, is also an intellectual suicide, let alone a scientific stupidity.)*

¹³Scientifically, they need to show that if those two origin scenarios are possible with experiments, then, the result should be accepted. Thus, if the COVID-19 is manmade or humanly manipulated and no one is willing to admit the responsibility, then, they will be facing their own God-Creator after their death and let us see how will they answer in front of God-Creator in the Great White Throne of God. No one get rid God after they die. As long as any human was formed in the mother's womb, the destiny of death also was already formed. Death is only the beginning of real life in eternity.

^{14/14}Let me **guide** you now, from the scientific explanatory power of the new Intelligent Design <id> on how to categorize COVID-19, from the science of the new Intelligent Design <id>.

GUIDE in CATEGORIZING THE COVID-19 SCIENTIFICALLY

^{1/6}The followings are expected from the scientific definition of *intelligence* to *non-intelligence* on the origin of the COVID-19 and who or which is the AGENT involved. Is the COVID-19 humanly manipulated to exist (intellen) or just happened with no human manipulation or zoonotic (naturen)? We will be looking for the responsible AGENT (human or not) for the existence of COVID-19.

²Here is the discovered scientific, universal, testable and applicable definition of both intelligence and non-intelligence.

Intelligence = when an agent uses/applies two or more solutions
to a single problem

Non-Intelligence = when an agent or designer uses/applies one solution,
or least number of solutions compared to other agents, to
a single problem

³Let me add, the definition of intelligence, in its application, requires the principles of intelligence so that “intelligence”, as a method, could be applied to any *X* by an AGENT, in our case today, the ***X = COVID-19***. Here are the discovered Principles of Intelligence as used by an agent. By using these principles of intelligence and knowing them, then we will also know how the Agent used them, therefore, we can conclude or predict with some accuracy which Agent originated the COVID-19. Know the principles of intelligence, know the Agent.

Principle 1. The Principle of Asymmetry

Principle 2. The Principle of Reinforcement or Support

Principle 3. The Principle of Importance

Principle 4. The Principle of Simultaneity of or in Time

Principle 5. The Principle of Applied Knowledge

Principle 6. The Principle of Success or Independence

Principle 7. The Principle of Existence, Survival, Success, and Life

Principle 8. The Principle of Determinism

⁴Take note that I had discussed these *Principles of Intelligence* in detailed in one of my science e-books discussing the discovery of “intelligence”. To those of you who had read one of my science e-books discussing *intelligence*, titled *The New Intelligent Design <id> Turning The Scientific World Upside Down*, (Link here: <https://www.amazon.com/Intelligent-Design-Turning-Scientific-Upside-ebook/dp/B00HWUX220>) I discussed them there. I cannot share them here for space limitation. These principles are essentials for the application of intelligence by an AGENT, the one who responsible for the existence of COVID-19, whether the COVID-19 is intellen or naturen.

⁵The definition of **intelligence** (see also the *non-intelligence*) points to many major topics. First

- (1), the Agent, then,
- (2) Problem, the
- (3) Solution and the
- (4) Application of solution/s.

^{6/6}Four major guides, but subdivided into many topics. But *intelligence* too has principles for applications, to be used for applications of solutions, thus, we will use them too as **guide** in categorizing if the COVID-19 is manmade intentionally (intelligently) or not.

An analogy of COVID-19 and a poisonous King Cobra. *There was a group of campers who had made and set up tents near the bank of the river. But in the middle of the night, they were shocked that some of the members had died. They found out that a King Cobra had bitten some of the members and still biting more. The question is: where did the King Cobra had come from? From the Jungle or river or from the one of the members whose habit is to collect King Cobra and study it?*

What We Know About COVID-19 and Its Origin?

¹Before we could use the power of the new Intelligent Design <id> in guiding us to know the unknown Agent in the origin of COVID-19, let us first know the Background of Events and the Reports from the government of China about the COVID-19, since, any scientist or any person who would like to categorize any *X* will surely gather and compile all available information or data, to help for correct categorization.

²It was the Chinese government on 2019 who had reported that the COVID-19 appeared and originated in Wuhan City, Hubei Province, based on the information gathered by the doctors or medical staffs in the Wuhan Hospital who had been dealing and curing the earliest infected patients of the COVID-19. The Chinese government had concluded that the *Wuhan Huanan Haixian Pifa Shichang* market was the epicenter of the COVID-19 virus outbreak and the Chinese government had logically closed it so that the market could no longer infect many people. This shows that the COVID-19 is not an ordinary coronavirus but a very strong and a very dangerous virus. The whole world understands and understood it.

³To tell you the truth, I believe and accept the Reports from the medical doctors and the Hospitals about the outbreak. I also believe and accept the testimonies or statements from the earliest COVID-19 infected patients that they had been to that market and/or has connection on that market. So that the initial patients' precious lives will be saved by the medical staffs and doctors from the COVID-19, the patients were surely willing to give the whole correct information on their past history before and after they got infected by the COVID-19. And the rest is history.

⁴So, which Agent brought the COVID-19 to Wuhan Market? There are 9 scenarios that we must check for the origin or Source of COVID-19 who had brought that virus in the Wuhan market, causing many innocent Chinese people to be

infected and some had died and spread around the world.

- ⁵**Scenario 1:** The seller of an unknown animals (with COVID-19) in the Market unknowingly brought the COVID-19 (zoonotic)?
- ⁶**Scenario 2:** COVID-19-infected-researchers of the COVID-19 went to Wuhan market and unknowingly infected other people in the market? These reserachers probably mishandled the COVID-19 when they went to caves (?) to search for the COVID-19, without wearing a biosafety or personal protection equipment (PPE) level 5 suits that could protect them from the strong virulency virus. They probably thought that the COVID-19 is a weak virus that there is no need to use a biosafety level 5 or higher suits?
- ⁷**Scenario 3:** A worker or staff in the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV) who was infected by the COVID-19 went to Wuhan Market to buy something (?) but infected other people in Wuhan market? The worker or staff may unknowingly or knowingly mishandle a very strong virus and dangerous virus, thinking that COVID-19 is a weak virus? A lab leak scenario?
- ⁸**Scenario 4:** Foreign secret operatives or enemies of China had planted the COVID-19 in the Wuhan Market and infected innocent Chinese people? The Chinese government is pointing to *Military World Games* held in Wuhan on October 18-27, 2019, attended by many military personnel around the world? Or probably by other means?
- ⁹**Scenario 5:** Tourists from other countries like Italy, Spain, France, Brazil Or USA, etc who had visited and traveled to Wuhan Market had unknowingly spread the COVID-19 from the tourists' country of origin and infected local Chinese?
- ¹⁰**Scenario 6:** An international package from other countries that contains COVID-19 was delivered somewhere in the Wuhan Market, mishandled by unsuspecting locals and got infected?
- ¹¹**Scenario 7:** The Chinese government had manipulated the COVID-19 to be

used as a tool to control the Chinese society and submit to the authority of the Communist Party? The CCP had chosen the Wuhan Market to indirectly blame the result from foreign military personnel joining the Games?

¹²**Scenario 8:** Alien invaders from outer space (maybe from Pluto?) had went to Wuhan Market, brought the COVID-19 and started attacking the Earth through the dangerous virus? Earth must surrender now or else...?

¹³**Scenario 9:** The God-Creator had created the COVID-19 and pinpointedly brought the virus to Wuhan Market to destroy the image of atheist China around the world(?) Payback time already??!

¹⁴Below was the response from the government of China through the *Global Times* about the possible origin of the COVID-19 in the US. It was published on August 3, 2021 in the website of the *Global Times*.

The image is a screenshot of a news article from the Global Times. At the top left, the 'GT Global Times' logo is visible. The article title is 'Questions linger over US COVID-19 origin tracing'. Below the title, the authors are listed as 'By Yu Tianjiao and Feng Qingyin' and the publication date is 'Published: Aug 03, 2021 11:40 PM'. There are social media sharing icons for Facebook, Twitter, WeChat, and Weibo. The main visual is a graphic with a dark background, featuring a glowing red and white virus particle on the left and a black silhouette of a person's head wearing a blue and white American flag patterned face mask on the right. The text 'Questions linger over US COVID-19 origin tracing' is overlaid on the graphic.

Infographic article from Global Times, discussing the origin of COVID-19

^{15/15}Below is the continuation of the Infographic picture made by the *Global Times*, discussing the possible origin of the COVID-19 in the US.

Questions linger over US COVID-19 origin tracing

Belleville mayor believes he and others contracted COVID-19 in November - more than a month before doctors in China first reported cases of the new disease.

A study of 7,000 blood collected among residents of 9 states in the US between December 13, 2019 and January 17, 2020 found antibodies to SARS-CoV-2, the virus that causes COVID-19, in the US.

In July 2019, the US CDC sent a letter to Fort Detrick, asking it to terminate most of its operations over security concerns.

One month later, problems with the disposal of dangerous materials led the US government to suspend infectious disease research being under-taken at Fort Detrick.

In July 2019, respiratory diseases of unknown origin began to appear in northern Virginia. The media reported on a large-scale outbreak of EVALI.

In September, Maryland reported number of patients showing EVALI symptoms had doubled. The illness presents symptoms very similar to COVID-19.

From January 1, 2015 to June 1, 2020, the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill reported a total of 28 lab safety incidents involving Gmos to the NIH, six of which involved lab-made multiple coronaviruses.

An American journalist claimed Maatje Benassi, a US military athlete, a member of the US delegation, may be patient zero.

In a report by the US Department of Defense official website in October 2019, Benassi participated in a 50-mile cycling road race in Wuhan.

On October 18, 2019, on the opening day of the 7th CISM Military World Games in Wuhan, Johns Hopkins University and the Gates Foundation held a pandemic tabletop exercise called "Event 201."

The exercise claimed to be designed to simulate responses to a new global coronavirus outbreak.

US media revealed that data for 171 patients who had symptoms or tested positive for COVID-19 in January and February 2020 was removed from the Florida Department of Health website on the night of May 4, 2020. The data disappeared until 19:30 the same day, but the time of the onset of symptoms was missing.

In March 12, 2020, US CDC director said at a hearing on Capitol Hill that some COVID-19 deaths have been diagnosed as flu-related in the US.

Infographic article from Global Times, discussing the origin of COVID-19, the main picture.

Guide 1: Problem

¹Since the goal of categorizing the COVID-19 is to find and pinpoint the unknown Agent, then, we need to skip the Agent in the definition and start the Categorization Guide from the “Problem”.

²In the definition of intelligence, *problem* is the second topic. For our unknown Agent, what was the Problem of the Agent? Why the Agent originated or existed the COVID-19? Why a very dangerous and wild COVID-19 exist and was detected in Wuhan Market infecting people, as reported by the medical staffs or doctors, and reported by the Chinese government? Who brought COVID-19 in the Wuhan Market and spread around the world?

End of Revision 1

(I will be continuing and finishing this science article in *Revision 2*. Thank you for reading.)